

Synthesis and characterization of polysulfonate of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)anthrone-10 and 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonyl chloride

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Cardo polysulfonate of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)anthrone-10 (0.005 mol) and 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonyl chloride (0.005 mol) has been synthesized by interfacial polycondensation by using water-dichloromethane (2 : 1 v/v) as an interphase, alkali (0.012 mol) as an acid acceptor and benzyl dimethyl hexadecyl ammonium chloride as an emulsifier. The reaction time and temperature were 3 h and 0°C, respectively. Polysulfonate is characterized by IR and NMR spectral data, viscosity in three different solvents and temperatures and density ($1.4972 \pm 0.002 \text{ g/cm}^3$). It possesses excellent solubility in common solvents, high T_g ($\sim 200^\circ\text{C}$), high thermal stability (371°C) and involved two-step decomposition. Calculated kinetic parameters : E_a , A , n and ΔS^* are $187.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $3.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$, 2.1, $-10.8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $150.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $4.6 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, 1.9, $-146.6 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. Large and negative magnitudes of ΔS^* have indicted ordered transition states.

Aromatic polysulfonates have received attention with regard to the production of high performance materials. Aromatic polysulfonates containing cardo groups occupy a prominent place amongst aromatic polyesters, polyamides, polyimides, polyethers and polycarbonates due to their outstanding physico-chemical properties such as good thermal stability, high T_g , good mechanical properties, excellent electrical properties, excellent solubility and hydrolytic stability towards acids, alkalis and salts^{1,2}.

A few work has been reported on aromatic polysulfonates containing 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonate moiety³. In continuation of our work, the present work describes the synthesis and physico-chemical properties of polysulfonate of 9,9'-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)anthrone-10 and 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonyl chloride (**1**)^{4,5} :

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Results and discussion

Spectral characterization : Observed characteristic IR absorption bands (cm^{-1}) of polysulfonate are 3423.4 (O-H str.), 1668.3 (-CO-str., ketone), 1417.6 (-SO₂-, ν_s), 1193.9 (-SO₂-, ν_{as}) besides normal modes of aromatic groups. The strong absorption at about 3423 cm^{-1} indicated a significant number of unreacted -OH groups indicating formation of moderate molecular weight of the polymer as supported by low intrinsic viscosity (Table 1). The NMR (CDCl_3) chemical shift (δ) and coupling constant are 6.895 (8H, d, Ar-H (a+b)), 6.996-6.972 (2H, d, Ar-H(f), J 7.3), 7.468-7.383 (4H, m, Ar-H (d+e), J 10.6, 7.8, 7.0), 7.760-7.732 (2H, d, Ar-H (h), J 8.4), 8.206-8.052 (4H, m Ar-H (i+j), J 6.5, 5.7), 8.25 (4H, s, Ar-H (c+g)). The signal due to residual CHCl_3 is appeared at about 7.26 ppm. The corresponding integrated protons are found in good agreement with theoretical number of protons and satisfactory coupling constant (J) are found for different types of protons.

Viscosity measurements : The solution viscosity is an important tool for understanding molecular interactions occurring in the solution and it is a direct measure of hydrodynamic volume of molecules. The least squares intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ and Huggins constant (k') of polysulfonate were determined in chloroform (CF); 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE), tetrahydrofuran (THF) at three different temperatures : 30°, 35° and 40°C; and are reported in Table 1. It is clear from Table 1 that polysulfonate

Table 1. The least squares intrinsic viscosity, Huggins constant and correlation coefficient of polysulfonate at three different temperatures and solvents

Chloroform			DCE			THF		
$[\eta]$	k'	γ	$[\eta]$	k'	γ	$[\eta]$	k'	γ
				30°C				
0.46	0.58	0.999	0.57	0.51	0.977	0.66	0.39	0.997
				35°C				
0.37	0.96	0.997	0.53	0.43	0.999	0.64	0.39	0.970
				40°C				
0.35	1.00	0.999	0.46	0.60	0.994	0.59	0.46	0.997

has low intrinsic viscosity indicating moderate molecular weight and as a result it formed brittle film from the solutions. On the basis of experimental observations, thermodynamic goodness of $[\eta]$ is THF > DCE > CF. The intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ has decreased and k' has increased with increasing temperature. Increase in k' with temperature indicated increase in solvent-polymer interactions in the solutions. Thus little solvent and temperature effect is found on polysulfonate under study.

Density measurements : The density of polymer under investigation was determined at room temperature according to reported method by using CCl₄-n-hexane binary system. Theoretical density was calculated according to Slonimskii *et al.*⁶. The experimental and theoretical densities are 1.4972 ± 0.0020 g/cm³ and 1.4279 g/cm³, respectively. The relative % error involved in the measurements is found to be 4.85% indicating right choice of packing coefficient ($K = 0.695$) for film samples.

Thermal analysis : Thermal analysis of polymers^{7,8} is of paramount importance since it furnishes knowledge about characteristic degradation pattern, molecular architecture, degradation mechanism, etc. and useful in designing materials for specific applications. DTA thermogram of polysulfonate showed change in slope at about 200°C, which might be due to T_g and two exotherms at 413.9°C and 704°C, which are due to decomposition reactions as supported by weight loss in T_g curve at these temperature ranges.

Polysulfonate is thermally stable up to about 371°C and involved two-step decomposition. There is a rapid weight loss over temperature ranges from 371–434°C and 616–754°C with temperature of maximum (T_{max}) weight loss 401°C and 712.4°C, respectively for first and second steps. The first step involved 27.9% weight loss while second step involved 58.8% weight loss. Polysulfonate under study possesses high thermal stability (371°C) as compared to other aromatic polysulfonates

of 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonyl chloride with other bisphenols such as bisphenol-A (325°C)³, bisphenol-C (354°C)⁴ and phenolphthalein (363°C)⁵. Thus the structure of bisphenols has affected thermal stability to a considerable extent.

The kinetic parameters E_a , A and n are determined according to method of Freeman-Anderson⁹ and ΔS^* is determined at corresponding T_{max} . The observed values of E_a , A , n and ΔS^* are 187.1 kJ mol⁻¹, 3.8×10^{12} s⁻¹, 2.1 and -10.6 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ and 150.7 kJ mol⁻¹, 4.6×10^5 s⁻¹, 1.9, -146.6 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively for first and second steps. Both the steps have followed second order decomposition reactions. High values of E_a indicated rigid nature of the polymer chains. A large and negative magnitudes of ΔS^* have indicated ordered transition states, which are rate determining steps.

The sulfonate and carbonyl linkages in the main chain are weak points, which degrade selectively to form free radicals. These radicals may further recombine to form new compound that may further degrade at higher temperature. The pyrolysis process of polymers is complex process and involves a variety of reactions like chain cleavage, rearrangement of chain segments, decomposition of chain segments, cross-linking, branching, etc.

In conclusion polysulfonate under investigation possesses excellent solubility in common organic solvents, high T_g and high thermal stability and involved two-step decomposition.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of laboratory grade and were purified prior to their use¹⁰. 9,9'-Bis(4-hydroxy phenyl)anthrone-10 (BAN)¹¹ and 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonyl chloride³ were synthesized according to reported methods and were repeatedly recrystallized from appropriate solvent systems. The emulsifier benzyl dimethyl hexadecyl ammonium chloride (Fluka, AG) was used as received.

Polymer synthesis : In a 250 ml three-necked flask equipped with a high-speed mechanical stirrer and a thermometer; a 0.005 mol BAN and 0.012 mol sodium hydroxide were dissolved in 25 ml distilled water and the solution was cooled to 0°C. A 50 mg benzyl dimethyl hexadecyl ammonium chloride was added and the solution was stirred vigorously for about 15 min. Then, a solution of 0.005 mol 3,3'-benzophenone disulfonyl chloride in 12.5 ml dichloromethane was added drop wise over 10 min. The emulsion was vigorously stirred for 3 h at 0°C. The organic layer was run into a large excess of methanol to precipitate the polymer. The separated polymer was filtered, washed well with water and finally washed with methanol and dried at 50°C. The polymer was further purified repeatedly by dissolving in chloroform and precipitating in methanol. The yield was ~83%. Polymer is highly soluble in common organic solvents like chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane, tetrahydrofuran, DMF, DMSO, etc. and formed brittle films from chloroform solution indicating moderate molecular weight.

Measurements : The IR spectrum (KBr pellet) of polysulfonate was scanned on a Carl-Zeiss Specord FTIR spectrophotometer and the NMR spectrum was scanned on a Bruker (300 MHz) FTNMR spectrometer by using CDCl₃ as a solvent and TMS as an internal standard. The viscosity measurements in different solvents at three different temperatures : 30°, 35° and 40°C were carried out with an Ubbelohde type suspended level viscometer¹² and intrinsic viscosities were determined by Huggins relationship¹³. The density of polysulfonate film was determined by floatation method according to our recent work¹⁴. TG-DTA measurements were made on a Mettler TS system at the heating rate of 15°C/min in an N₂ atmosphere.

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References

1. V. V. Korshak, V. Svetlana, S. V. Vinogradova and Y. S. Vygodskii, *J. Macromol. Sci.*, 1974, **C11**, 45.
2. M. Podgorskii and W. Podkoscielny, *Pol Pl.*, 1981, **100**, 187 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, **96**, 122395).
3. J. L. Work and J. E. Herweh, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1968, **A16**, 2022.
4. A. R. Shah and P. H. Parsania, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1997, **14**, 171.
5. D. R. Godhani, M. R. Sanariya, Y. V. Patel and P. H. Parsania, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 2002, **38**, 2171.
6. G. L. Slonimskii, A. A. Askadskii and A. I. Kitaigorodskii, *Vysokomol. Soyed.*, 1970, **A12**, 494.
7. W. W. Wendlandt, "Thermal Methods of Analysis", 2nd ed., Wiley, New York, 1974.
8. T. Meisel and K. Seytold, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1981, **12**, 267.
9. E. S. Freeman and D. A. Anderson, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1961, **54**, 253.
10. A. Weissberger and S. S. Proskaur (eds.), "Techniques of Organic Solvents", Interscience, New York, 1955.
11. S. V. Vinogradova, S. N. Salazkin, L. A. Beridze, A. I. Mzhel'skii, A. A. Askadskii, G. L. Slonimskii and V. V. Korshak, *Vysokomol Soyed*, 1969, **A11**, 27; *Polym. Sci. USSR*, 1969, **11**, 27.
12. L. J. Ubbelohde, *Inst. Pet. London*, 1935, **19**, 376.
13. M. L. Huggins, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 2716.
14. F. D. Karia and P. H. Parsania, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1999, **35**, 121.